

ENHANCING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CAN BE ACHIEVED BY INCORPORATING AUTHENTIC TEXTS INTO THE TEACHING PROCESS

Dilrabo Maxmutjonovna Mamatova

Namangan State University English teacher

dilrabomamatova@gmail.com

+998972566536

Abstract

The article is devoted to the actual problem of using authentic materials in the process of teaching a foreign language. The use of authentic materials is considered as one of the basic requirements of a communicative approach, a specific feature of which is the desire to bring the language learning process as close as possible to the process of real communication, as well as a necessary condition for the formation of the sociocultural component of communicative competence. Features of integration of web resources into the process of teaching reading for specific information are considered. Methodological recommendations for teaching this type of reading are given

Key words: criteria, authenticity, authentic materials, factor, authentic material

Абстракт

Статья посвящена актуальной проблеме использования аутентичных материалов в процессе обучения иностранному языку. Использование аутентичных материалов рассматривается как одно из основных требований коммуникативного подхода, специфической особенностью которого является стремление максимально приблизить процесс изучения языка к процессу реального общения, а также необходимое условие формирования социокультурного компонента коммуникативной компетентности. Рассмотрены особенности интеграции веб-ресурсов в процесс обучения чтению конкретной информации. Даны методические рекомендации по обучению этому виду чтения.

Ключевые слова: критерии, аутентичность, аутентичные материалы, фактор, аутентичный материал.

Abstrakt

Maqola chet tilini o'qitish jarayonida autentik materiallardan foydalanishning dolzarb muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Autentik materiallardan foydalanish kommunikativ yondashuvning asosiy talablaridan biri sifatida qaraladi, uning o'ziga xos xususiyati til o'rganish jarayonini real muloqot jarayoniga imkon qadar yaqinlashtirish istagi, shuningdek bu kommunikativ kompetentsiyaning ijtimoiy-madaniy komponentini shakllantirish uchun zarur shartdir. Autentik ma'lumotlarni o'qib o'rganish jarayoniga veb-resurslarni integratsiyalash xususiyatlari ko'rib bu maqolada ko'rib chiqiladi va ushbu turdagi o'qib o'rgatish bo'yicha uslubiy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mezonlar, haqiqiylik, haqiqiy materiallar, omil, haqiqiy material

Introduction

Currently, the goal of teaching a foreign language is the achievement of communicative competence for subsequent communication with native speakers of this language. An important task of a teacher is to create real and imaginary situations of communication in a foreign language lesson using various working methods. Nowadays authentic materials are of great importance. The increased attention to the problems of teaching foreign languages is due to the fact that the main information and communication load falls on the language.

Communicative pragmatic orientation determines the content of training, what communicative skills must be formed so that the student can communicate verbally and in writing. For example: say hello, give advice, consult with someone, while you need to master the speech system to perform communication tasks, for example: how to say who you are, what you do, how to find out about something; how to understand the text at the level of meaning and at the level of meaning; what strategy to choose in reading, based on the goal that the reader sets; how to “squeeze” the text to convey the main thing.

Modern English reality is reflected in authentic materials. Authors relate to authentic materials articles, popular science texts, personal letters, and interviews, excerpts from diaries, fairy tales, advertisements, jokes, recipes and country texts. They emphasize the preservation of the authenticity of the genre and the fact that genre-compositional diversity allows students to learn about speech cliches, vocabulary, phraseology related to the most diverse spheres of life and belonging to different styles. Today, a lot of authentic texts are given in the methodology of teaching a foreign language

Discussion

There are several selection principles and approaches to determining authenticity. The main criteria of authenticity is considered to be functionality, i.e. orientation of authentic materials to everyday use, creating the illusion of familiarization with the natural language environment, which is the basis of factor in the successful development of a foreign language. Work on functionally authentic material communicates the student to the actual conditions of use language, introduces him to a variety of linguistic- by my means and prepares for independent use the consumption of these funds in speech. Teaching a second foreign language helps to build intercultural communication skills. The principle taken as the basis for teaching multilingualism is based on the positive influence of one studied foreign language on another, i.e. on the phenomenon of transfer of skills, abilities and tactical and strategic communicative behavior. Authentic texts can be useful in teaching a foreign language, as they often reflect a more modern situation in the world than educational materials in their native language, and therefore will be more interesting students. Authentic materials also help to dispel students' doubts about the practical use of a foreign language. The use of authentic texts in the process of teaching a foreign language in elementary school can have a different character — teaching the culture of the country of the language being studied. This is possible when using in the lessons in the case of teaching a foreign language children school age songs, fairy tales and other

fiction intended for children of the specified age group. The difficulty of teaching younger students is that if the preschool period is characterized mainly by game forms of cognition of the surrounding reality, then they are subsequently replaced by the educational form of activity and it is necessary for the primary school teacher in the learning process to ensure the transition from game activity to educational.

One of the most popular and highly effective types of educational activities is the game. Game activity is used in learning for all ages, but since it was for primary school students that game activity was still prevailing quite recently, we will consider it in relation to children of primary school age. According to R.S. Nemova, the game “improves the objective activity, logic and methods of thinking, forms and develops the skills and business interactions with people”, and the communication that occurs during this game, “improves the exchange of information, improves the communicative structure of intelligence, and teaches to correctly perceive, understand and evaluate “interlocutors. Equally, important is the development of foreign language communication skills among students. In this case, the game can simulate various speech situations, allowing preparing for the practical application of the received in a knowledge lesson. It is widely known that the more playing techniques a teacher uses, the more interesting are lessons and the stronger the material is fixed.

During the lesson the game is only a form of the educational task, which includes the linguistic, communicative and activity task. The game is considered as an exercise in which the opportunity is created for repeated repetition of the speech sample in conditions as close as possible to real communication with its inherent signs — the emotionally and purposefulness of the speech effect. Analysis of modern research on the problem of using the game in educational activities, allows Separates games into two sections. The first section is “Preparatory Games”, contributing to the formation of speech skills. These include grammar, lexical, phonetic and spelling. Training students in the use of grammatical structures, requiring their repeated repetition, tires students of uniformity, and the effort expended does not bring quick satisfaction. Games will help to make boring work more interesting and exciting. Behind grammar is followed by lexical games, logically proper “build” the foundation of speech. Phonetic games are intended to adjust the pronunciation at the stage the formation of speech skills. And finally, for the development and development of speech and pronunciation skills to some extent spelling games whose main goal is the development of the spelling of the studied vocabulary. Most games in the first section can be used as training exercises at the stage both primary and further consolidation. The second section is “Creative Games”. The purpose of these games is to further the development of speech skills and skills. The ability to show independence in decision scientific and research tasks, quick reaction in communication, maximum mobilization of speech skills — characteristic qualities of speech skill — may, in our opinion, be manifested in auditory and speech games. Second Games section train students in the ability to creatively use call up speech skills.

A creative approach in educational activities is realized through role-playing games. It should be noted that the role playing game in the lesson should be organized in such a way that students can make the most of the vocabulary and speech constructs worked out in the lesson. During the role-playing game, not only the words “roles” are pronounced, but also certain associated actions are performed that help relieve the tension that often arises in the process of speaking. In addition, this largely gives the game realism along with entourage, which attracts the attention of students and helps to become interested in the game process. It is important to note that in combination with game activity, authentic sources are easier to learn and better absorbed by schoolchildren, since the game is a strong motivating factor. On the basis of literary texts, linguistic — phonetic, lexical, grammatical skills are formed. The development and improvement of skills in all types of speech activity — listening, speaking, reading, writing. At what stage in the training can literary texts be introduced? To work with educational and literary texts, it is recommended to use different types of reading: introductory, learning, viewing. Thus, for the most effective reference to fiction, students must have sufficient knowledge of the technique of familiarization and studying reading. At the initial stage, learning to read is preferred. With this type of reading, the most complete study of the information contained in the text occurs. The difference between literary texts and other texts used in the educational process is their authenticity, since they are not created specifically for teaching. This, in turn, also presents certain difficulties for the understanding of texts by foreign students. So, a literary text, like any other text, is a unit of instruction. The main goal of such work in the lesson is understanding the text, its emotional perception. The achievement of this goal is largely facilitated by the described forms of working with text. At the final stage, a discussion is organized on topic covered. Thus, the lesson implements a combination of competency, value and activity approaches to civic education of students using a foreign language. Among the objective results of mastering the educational program in the section “Communicative skills”, this type of speech activity, such as reading, is especially distinguished. The need to use information and information and communication technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language is undeniable, therefore the widely discussed topic of many modern researchers is the use of web resources for teaching foreign languages. An introductory reading is a cognitive reading when the entire text becomes the subject of the reader’s attention: there is no installation for specific information. The main communicative task: extract basic information. Such reading requires the development of the ability to differentiate the main and secondary information. Learning to read involves a complete and accurate understanding of the information contained in the text, and its critical reflection. The task of a student of reading is to form the learner’s ability to independently overcome difficulties in understanding a foreign language.

Literature review

The object of study is the information contained in the text, and not the language material. View reading involves gaining a general understanding of the topic and range of issues addressed in the text. Search reading is aimed at finding in a text or in an array of texts specific data (indications, indicators, facts), i.e. specific information. Such reading presupposes the presence of the ability to navigate in the logical-semantic structure of the text, to select and combine the information contained in several texts. In an educational setting, search reading is an exercise. Mastering the reading technology is carried out as a result of pretext, text and post-text tasks. Pretext tasks are aimed at eliminating probabilistic (supposed) semantic and linguistic difficulties in understanding the text and at the same time on the formation of reading and reading skills. Text jobs offer communicative settings, which contain indications of the type of reading and the need to solve cognitive communicative tasks. Post-text exercises are designed to test reading comprehension.

Our study focuses on search reading and involves working with authentic text. E.G. Azimov and A.N. Schukin offer the following definition of the concept “Authentic text”: “... oral and written text, which is a real product of speech activity of native speakers and not adapted for the needs of students, taking into account their level of language proficiency”. The most reliable example of authentic text today are web resources. Among them can be distinguished such as: ebay.com, amazon.com and.com. These resources are online trading platforms where English-speaking sellers put up for auction their goods and services. Potential customers leave feedback and comments about the product using a “live” spoken language. When learning search reading at the middle stage, forest use these web resources when exploring lexical topics: clothing, gifts, sports, shopping, etc. As with any other type of reading, search reading using web resources involves three stages: pretext, text and post-text and follows the principle of “from simple to complex” in the distribution of exercises. The pretext stage of teaching search reading using web resources (in particular, online trading sites) can consist of exercises such as “highlight keywords in the headings of the ads”, “use the keywords to determine the category of the lot”, “compare the picture with the heading of the ad”. Thus, the final task of the pretext stage will already make it possible to judge the degree of formation of the search reading ability. The text stage may include tasks such as “find answers to questions”, “collect keywords by sections”. Searching for specific information on the online auction page develops search reading skills, and identifying keywords in sections expands vocabulary and contributes to a deeper understanding of the lexical topic. At the post-text stage, the degree of formation of the search reading ability is controlled.

Conclusion

So, it may consist in filling out a table for several announcements. Learners may be offered collect information about the price, condition of the lot, seller, the rate and

policy of returns. Our study allows us to suggest that the use of web resources, which are trading Internet sites, in a foreign language lesson provides increased motivation for students, “provokes” them to use meta-subject skills, helps to overcome language a barrier through the usual for many activities, the so-called “Internet surfing.”

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